

NUTRI•KNOW

STRUVITE (IT)

RENURE (BE)

GAS LOOP (IT)

POCKETBOER 2 (BE)

SOS_AQUAE (IT)

Grass2Algae (BE)

FERTICOOP-GO (ES)

MOPS (IE)

Manure Management Tool (ES)

Duncannon Blue Flag Farming (IE)

Slurry Concentrator (ES)

Biorefinery Glas (IE)

Exchanging easy-to-understand nutrient management knowledge with farmers

NUTRI-KNOW aims to improve nutrient management practices in agriculture by establishing an ongoing cycle of knowledge exchange for the benefit of both farmers and the environment.

RENURE

REcoverd Nitrogen from manURE

RENURE aims to prepare the agricultural sector for the use of ammonium salt fertilisers (ammonium nitrate and ammonium sulphate) by making the transition from research-based field trials to a practical evaluation at the farmer's premises.

Main challenges

The Flemish agricultural sector faces a paradoxical scenario: while there is an excess of animal nutrients available, additional nutrients are being introduced in the form of fertilisers.

Ammonium salts as RENURE products

In 2020, the European Commission proposed the "RENURE" criteria to allow the safe use of recovered nitrogen from manure as a replacement for chemical fertilisers. Ammonium salts recovered from manure can be used as a priority RENURE product.

Field application

Five field trials were set up in 2022 and one in 2023 to evaluate ammonium nitrate recovered from animal manure through stripping and scrubbing process.

Results

- The ammonium nitrate recovered from animal manure performs as well as artificial fertilisers in terms of effectiveness and fertilising value.
- Applying ammonium nitrate with a row tiller or with injection is preferred as a low-emission method over application with a spray boom
- The status of animal manure in the current regulations is limited for ammonium nitrate application

Field injector for ammonium salts

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our journey!

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